

Voltammetric Studies of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) in Molten Urea and Thiourea at Solid Electrodes

KAMLESH KUMAR BANSAL and M. L. ANAND*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-132 119

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The Q-values of the oscillograms of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) in molten urea and thiourea at the stationary solid electrodes have been measured and interpreted in conjunction with D. C. polarograms obtained in forward and reverse direction of polarisation. Platinum, graphite and stainless steel electrodes have been employed *in situ*. The observed potential differences between Pt and graphite couple in presence of 0.1 M LiClO₄ in urea and thiourea are 0.045 and 0.015 V, respectively.

UREA and thiourea and its derivatives find a number of applications in agriculture, rubber vulcanization, electro-deposition of metals, corrosion inhibition, polymer and textile industries. Urea is physiologically important and possesses some double bond character (about 28%) in its C-N bond, which has been explained by resonance structures¹. Many of the reactions with acid chlorides or anhydrides yielding ureides, and formation of urea-formaldehyde resins may be attributed to resonance and removal of product from the resonating structures. Thiourea behaves similar to urea as far as the structure is concerned. However, oxidising agents like alkaline KMnO₄ replace sulphur with oxygen whereas reducing agents remove hydrogen sulphide to form cyanamide. Because of such properties it is used as a rubber vulcanisation accelerator and in synthesis of thiol compounds used as drugs. The mechanism of oxidation-reduction of urea and thiourea has been the subject of many investigations². Several excellent accounts of the electrochemistry of molten salts have been published^{3,4} but very few reports are available as regards organic melts.

Voltammetry and oscillography may be good techniques to give some indication of the oxidation-reduction of the species formed during electron transfer mechanism. The frequency of alternating current and the rate of resonating structures may give some clue to the mechanism of reactions occurring with proton donating species. Earlier Anand⁵ and Bansal and Anand⁶ reported the study of alkali metals in molten acetamide and voltammetric studies of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) in molten acetanilide. The present work is an attempt to obtain conditions for oxidation-reduction of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) in urea and thiourea at 145 and 195°, respectively with different stationary solid electrodes with the object of throwing some light on corrosion inhibition and mechanism of the process.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of analytical or reagent grade. D.C. polarograms were recorded as already

reported⁷. An electrical circuit used for polarizing the electrode with a controlled A.C. was fabricated according to Heyrovsky and Kalvoda⁸ with some modification as reported earlier⁹. Some representative photographs of the oscillograms of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) in molten urea and thiourea at 145 and 195° in presence of LiClO₄ are shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

Electrodes and pretreatment: Fabrication of electrodes and their pretreatment have already been reported¹⁰. The procedure of pretreatment followed was that due to Bruckenstein and coworkers¹¹.

Results and Discussion

Effect of electrodes: In D.C. polarography the current-voltage curves in forward and reverse direction of polarisation using LiClO₄ as supporting electrolyte in urea melt at 145° have been obtained. Platinum-graphite (Fig. 3) and steel-graphite (Fig. 4) electrode assemblies in urea melt with and without the supporting electrolyte have been used to record current-voltage curves.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Graphite/steel electrode system could not give stable and reproducible D.C. polarograms because of chemical reaction of steel at surface with thiourea at the temperature of the melt. However, current-voltage curves with Pt/Gr assembly in molten thiourea at 195° have been obtained (Fig. 5).

Many studies of electrode processes in melts are not sufficiently refined. Any large and unreactive conductor such as Pt¹², graphite¹³ etc., immersed in the melt will function as non-polarizable and hence *in situ* may be readily employed as reference. The behaviour of graphite electrode as anode and as a reference appears more well defined in conjunction with platinum electrode than steel.

In case of Pt/Gr assembly poor waves have been recorded in the forward direction of polarisation when Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) were added to urea-LiClO₄ system and the values of slope, when compared with those calculated theoretically following Delimarskii *et al*¹⁴, differed widely indicating a greater irreversibility and some surface phenomenon. Co(II) and Ni(II) in urea and Fe(III) and Ni(II) in thiourea behaved more irreversibly. The values of slope do not agree to diffusion controlled process (Table 1).

TABLE 1—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS AND VALUES OF SLOPE OBTAINED FOR Fe, Co AND Ni WITH RESPECT TO GRAPHITE. SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTE: LiClO₄ AND MELTS: UREA AND THIOUREA AT 145° AND 195°, RESPECTIVELY

Compound	$-E_{1/2}$	$-E_{1/2}$	Slope		Slope theoretical*	Value of n
	F	B	Observed F	B		
Urea	—	—	—	—	—	—
+LiClO ₄	—	—	—	—	190	1 (For Li ⁺)
FeCl ₃	0.23	0.225	133	128	190	1
					95	2
					63.3	3
CoCl ₂	0.34	—	128	—	190	1
					95	2
NiCl ₂	0.398	—	125	—	190	1
					95	2
Thiourea	—	—	—	—	—	—
+LiClO ₄	—	—	—	—	213	1 (For Li ⁺)
FeCl ₃	0.081	0.079	270	238	213	1
					106.5	2
					71	3
CoCl ₂	0.31	0.306	322	185	213	1
					106.5	2
NiCl ₂	0.131	0.08	454	322	213	1
					106.5	2

*Due to Delimarskii *et al*.

Fig. 3. Current-voltage curves in urea melt of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) with Pt/Gr assembly. Curve (1) urea, (2) urea+LiClO₄, (3) +Fe(III), (4) +Co(II) and (5) +Ni(II) in forward direction of polarisation; curves with dashed numbers are in the reverse.

Fig. 4. Current-voltage curves in urea melt of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) with steel/Gr assembly. Curve (1) urea, (2) urea + LiClO₄, (3) + Fe(III), (4) + Co(II) and (5) + Ni(II) in forward direction of polarisation; curves with dashed numbers are in the reverse.

Fig. 5. Current-voltage curves in thiourea melt of Fe(III), Co(II) and Ni(II) with Pt/Gr assembly. Curve (1) thiourea, (2) thiourea + LiClO₄, (3) + Fe(III), (4) + Co(II) and (5) + Ni(II) in forward direction of polarisation; curves with dashed numbers are in the reverse.

There appears no marked effect of LiClO₄ concentration between 0.05 to 0.25 M on the observed values of potential differences of the Pt/Gr couple. The observed potential differences in presence of 0.1 M LiClO₄ in urea and thiourea at 145 and 195° are 0.045 and 0.015 V, respectively.

Q-values: According to Heyrovsky⁹ the quotient Q is more useful than the value of potential which gives the relative position of indentation on the

derivative curve $dE/dt=f(E)$. The upper part of the derivative curve represents a cathodic process, and the lower one an anodic process. The Q-values vary between 0 and 1 and are independent of the reference electrode as reported by Heyrovsky. Accordingly, we have given the Q-values of all indentations on both parts viz. cathodic and anodic in Table 2. On comparing the Q-values of the cathodic and anodic parts of the derivative curve

TABLE 2-Q-VALUES OF Fe, Co AND Ni IN UREA AND THIOUREA MELTS AT 145° AND 195° IN PRESENCE OF LiClO₄ AT Pt/Gr ASSEMBLY

System	Cathodic			Anodic			Photo No.
	1	2	3	1	2	3	
Urea	—	0.433	—	—	0.50	—	1 (Fig 1)
LiClO ₄	0.133	—	0.866	0.2	0.533	—	2
FeCl ₃	0.136	0.454	0.863	0.206	0.590	0.772	3
CoCl ₂	0.24	0.40	0.72	0.24	0.52	0.76	4
NiCl ₂	0.218	0.468	0.718	0.25	0.625	0.812	5
Thiourea	—	—	0.703	—	—	0.740	1 (Fig. 2)
LiClO ₄	—	—	0.605	—	—	0.605	2
FeCl ₃	0.194	—	0.383	0.194	—	0.638	3
CoCl ₂	0.20	0.433	0.70	0.167	0.367	0.667	4
NiCl ₂	0.40	—	0.72	0.28	—	0.68	5

Potential axis range=1.35 V and 1.60 V for urea and thiourea, respectively

$dE/dt=f(E)$, we find some differences which may be attributed to some irreversibility and also to faster rate of redox process than the frequency of A.C. polarisation. The negatively charged atom in the resonating structures of urea

is capable of coordinating with one proton giving rise to "monoacidic base". Since the applied

frequency of alternating current is 50 Hz and the rate of resonating structure probably much faster than the processes occurring at the surface of electrode, true resonating stationary pattern could not be observed. However, some thorn like indentations may be noticed in case of urea melt. This gives some indication of the possibility of corrosion inhibition at the surface of electrode by urea. Laitinen and Gaur¹⁵ postulated adsorption on platinum for Co and Ni in fused salts in order to account for phase angles in their studies of Faradaic impedance. In an earlier paper we reported a similar behaviour of cobalt in molten acetanilide⁶ but there appears no such phenomenon in thiourea.

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